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UTICAJ EKSPLOATACIJE ŠLJUNKA I PESKA NA REŽIM POVRŠINSKIH I PODZEMNIH VODA

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Aptrakt:

Doline i aluvijoni većih reka oduvek su imali i imaju najpovoljnije uslove za život. Drevne civilizacije svoje naseobine vezivale su za obale reka. Danas u ovim delovima smeštena je većina prestonica i gradova u svetu. Glavni razlozi za ovo su: značajne rezerve podzemnih voda koje su formirane u okviru intergranularne sredine i koje su u dobroj hidrauličkoj vezi sa površinskim tokovima, omogućuju na lak način rešavanje vodosnabdevanja; visokokvalitetno zemljište i prisutne podzemne vode omogućuju intenzivnu poljoprivrednu proizvodnju; prisustvo značajnih rezervi peska i šljunka na obalama reka su velika podrška građevinarstvu; sam površinski tok pruža mogućnost uspostavljanja rečnog saobraćaja, odnosno povezivanje uzvodnih i nizvodnih delova sliva. Legalno i kontrolisano korišćenje pomenutih prirodnih potencijala reke i njenih obala ne bi trebalo da ima negativnog uticaja na bilo koji pomenut resurs. Međutim, nekontrolisano korišćenje pesticida i đubriva radi što veće poljoprivredne proizvodnje ima značajnog uticaja na kvalitet podzemnih voda, kao i nekontrolisana a u nekim slučajevima i nelegalna eksploatacija šljunka i peska može imati krajnje negativne posledice po vodosnabdevanje kao i navodnjavanje poljoprivrednih površina. Primera za pomenuto ima dosta i u svetu i kod nas. Jedan od primera kod nas je nekontrolisana i nelegalna eksploatacija šljunka i peska u delu kod Ljubičevskog mosta gde je tokom 90-tih godina došlo do produblivanja korita Velike Morave u iznosu od 4 m što je uticalo na rezerve podzemnih voda u ovom delu i njihov kvalitet. Kao posledica pomenutog izvorište „Ključ” je zbog povećane koncentracije nitrata u podzemnim vodama moralo biti 2006 godine isključeno iz sistema za vodosnabdevanje Požarevca, dok izvorište Trnovče (vodosnabdevanje Velike Plane i Smederevske Palanke) radi sa smanjenim eksploatacionim kapacitetom. Ako posmatramo reku Drinu koja u svom donjem delu predstavlja i državnu granicu Republike Srbije (RS) i Bosne i Hercegovine (BiH), nekontrolisana eksploatacija dovela je do rušenja obala, pomeranja matice reke pa samim tim i izmeštanja korita ove reke što je dovelo do toga da sada delovi RS se nalaze na levoj obali reke i obrnuto. O ovome kao i o drugim negativnim uticajima nelegalne i nekontrolisane eksploatacije šljunka i peska biće detaljnije izloženo u radu.

Ključne reči: eksploatacija šljunka i peska, režim voda, podzemne vode, vodosnabdevanje

IMPACT OF GRAVEL AND SAND EXPLOITATION ON SURFACE AND GROUNDWATER REGIME

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Abstract:

Floodplains and alluviums of larger rivers have always had, and still have, the most favorable living conditions. Ancient civilizations established their settlements along riverbanks. Today, most of the world's capitals and cities are located in these areas. The main reasons for this are: significant reserves of groundwater formed within the intergranular aquifers, which are in good hydraulic connection with surface flows and enable relatively simple solutions for water supply; high-quality soil and the presence of groundwater enable intensive agricultural production; the presence of significant reserves of sand and gravel on the riverbanks greatly supports construction; the surface flow itself provides the possibility of establishing river transportation, i.e., connecting the upstream and downstream parts of the basin. Legal and controlled use of the mentioned natural resources of the river and its banks should not have a negative impact on any of the mentioned resources. However, uncontrolled use of pesticides and fertilizers for the sake of higher agricultural production significantly impacts the quality of groundwater, as well as uncontrolled and, in some cases, illegal exploitation of gravel and sand can have extremely negative consequences for water supply and the irrigation of agricultural land. There are many examples of this, both in the world and in our country. One example from Serbia is the uncontrolled and illegal exploitation of gravel and sand in the area of the Ljubičevski Bridge, where during the 1990s the riverbed of the Velika Morava deepened by 4 meters. This affected the reduction of groundwater reserves in this area and the deterioration of their quality. As a consequence of this, the 'Ključ' water source had to be excluded from the Požarevac water supply system in 2006 due to increased nitrate concentrations in the groundwater, while the 'Trnovče' water source (for the water supply of Velika Plana and Smederevska Palanka) operates with reduced exploitation capacity. Observing the Drina River, which in its lower part represents the international border between the Republic of Serbia (RS) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH), uncontrolled exploitation of gravel and sand led to the collapse of the riverbanks, shifting of the river current, and consequently, the relocation of the riverbed, resulting in parts of RS now being on the left bank of the river and vice versa. This, along with other negative impacts of illegal and uncontrolled exploitation of gravel and sand, will be elaborated in detail in the paper

Keywords: gravel and sand exploitation, water regime, groundwater, water supply